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ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

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INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF MICE TOURISM AND ITS ADAPTATION TO THE CONDITIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. MICE business tourism is one of the most dynamic segments of the global tourism industry. For Uzbekistan, it is of particular importance in terms of diversifying the tourism product and positioning the country as a regional hub for business communications. The study aims to identify, on the basis of international experience, the key components of competitive MICE destinations and to propose a model for their adaptation to the conditions of Uzbekistan. The methods include literature review, documentary analysis, comparison of infrastructural and institutional characteristics, and interpretation of multiplier effects. The findings show that the output multiplier of MICE events reaches 2.94 in China and about 2.84 in Kazakhstan, which suggests a comparable potential for Uzbekistan. The paper substantiates the need to establish a Convention Bureau, to expand hybrid formats, to deepen regional cooperation and to apply GSTC and ICCA criteria in order to strengthen the institutional foundations of the sector.

Keywords: MICE tourism; business events; conference tourism; exhibitions; economic impact; tourism infrastructure; Convention Bureau; Uzbekistan; Central Asia.

Annotatsiya. MICE formatidagi biznes-turizm jahon turizm industriyasining eng dinamik segmentlaridan biridir. O'zbekiston uchun u turistik mahsulotni diversifikatsiya qilish va mamlakatni mintaqaviy biznes-kommunikatsiyalar markazi sifatida pozitsiyalash nuqtai nazaridan alohida ahamiyatga ega. Tadqiqotning maqsadi – xalqaro tajriba tahlili asosida raqobatbardosh MICE yo'nalishlarining asosiy tarkibiy elementlarini ajratib ko'rsatish va ularni O'zbekiston sharoitiga moslashtirish modelini taklif etish. Metodlar: adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish, hujjatli tahlil, infratuzilma va institutsional xususiyatlarni taqqoslash, multiplikativ effektlarni talqin qilish. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, MICE tadbirlarining multiplikatori Xitoyda 2,94 ga, Qozog'istonda taxminan 2,84 ga yetadi, bu esa O'zbekiston uchun ham shunga yaqin salohiyatni bashorat qilish imkonini beradi. Convention Bureau tashkil etish, gibrid formatlarni rivojlantirish, mintaqaviy hamkorlikni chuqurlashtirish hamda sektorni institutsional mustahkamlash maqsadida GSTC va ICCA mezonlaridan foydalanish zarurligi asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: MICE-turizm; biznes-turizm; konferensiya va ko'rgazmalar; iqtisodiy ta'sir; infratuzilma; Convention Bureau; O'zbekiston.

Аннотация. Деловой туризм формата MICE – один из самых динамичных сегментов мировой туристской индустрии. Для Узбекистана он важен с точки зрения диверсификации турпродукта и позиционирования страны как регионального центра деловых коммуникаций. Цель исследования – на основе анализа международного опыта выделить ключевые элементы конкурентоспособных MICE-направлений и предложить модель их адаптации к условиям Узбекистана. Методы: обзор литературы, документальный анализ, сопоставление инфраструктурных и институциональных характеристик, интерпретация мультипликативных эффектов. Показано, что мультипликатор MICE-событий достигает 2,94 в Китае и около 2,84 в Казахстане, что позволяет ожидать сопоставимый потенциал и для Узбекистана. Обосновывается необходимость создания Convention Bureau, развития гибридных форматов, углубления регионального сотрудничества и использования критериев GSTC и ICCA для институционального укрепления сектора.

Ключевые слова: деловой туризм; MICE-туризм; конференционный туризм; выставочная деятельность; экономическое развитие; туристская инфраструктура; Convention Bureau; мультипликативный эффект; Узбекистан; Центральная Азия.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, MICE tourism has evolved from a niche segment of corporate travel into one of the principal drivers of structural modernization in host destinations. Global assessments indicate not only the substantial scale of the MICE industry but also its consistently high growth rates: projections through 2031 suggest an expansion from USD 2.68 trillion to USD 10.41 trillion, with an average annual growth of approximately 21 percent (REAN Intelligence, 2024; Technavio, 2025). A characteristic feature of this segment is the significantly higher expenditure per business traveler compared to leisure tourists, as well as the complex composition of consumed services. Beyond accommodation and food services, MICE visitors generate demand for event organization, technical support, interpretation, business and educational programs, and cultural activities. Consequently, MICE tourism stimulates demand across a wide array of sectors and deepens the integration of tourism into broader economic systems.

For Central Asian countries, the MICE segment functions as a tool for diversifying the tourism sector and enhancing the resilience of economic growth by shifting from predominantly leisure-oriented routes to higher-yield and knowledge-intensive forms of tourism (Akbar et al., 2024; Ubaydullayeva, 2025). Uzbekistan possesses several foundational advantages, including its rich cultural and historical heritage associated with the Silk Road, its strategic transit position, and its growing participation in international economic processes. According to Musaeva (2024), around 150 international MICE conferences were held in the country in 2023, each hosting on average about 2,000 participants, while MICE-sector revenues reached USD 100 million, representing a 15 percent increase compared to 2022. Simultaneously, the formation of core MICE infrastructure has accelerated through the introduction of congress and exhibition centers and specialized venues with a total capacity of approximately 10,000 delegates.

There remains a mismatch between the dynamism of the sector and the extent of its theoretical conceptualization: existing scholarship lacks integrated studies that jointly examine destination competitiveness, institutional frameworks, multiplier effects, and regional cooperation (Musaeva, 2024; Ubaydullayeva, 2025). The objective of this study is therefore to identify the key structural elements of successful MICE destinations based on international experience and to substantiate a model for their adaptation to Uzbekistan's context, with particular emphasis on economic outcomes and institutional mechanisms. To achieve this goal, the study examines definitions and components of MICE tourism, criteria for destination competitiveness, the role of Convention Bureaus and industry standards, the magnitude of multiplier effects, and the specifics of regional cooperation in Central Asia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Contemporary scholarship defines MICE tourism as a specialized form of business travel that encompasses meetings, incentive trips, conferences, and exhibitions, all united by the logic of professional communication and knowledge exchange (Musaeva, 2024). The "meetings" component includes negotiations, seminars, and managerial sessions that facilitate horizontal linkages among participants. Incentive travel involves motivational programs and reward-oriented trips aimed at enhancing employee and partner loyalty. Conferences serve as platforms for discussing scientific, sectoral, and corporate agendas, whereas exhibitions support product demonstration, innovation promotion, and contract negotiation.

Destination competitiveness is often analyzed through the SFAA model (Services, Facilities, Amenities, Attractions), which has been successfully applied, including in the Indonesian context (Yuniati, 2025). Within this framework, competitiveness is determined by the combination of high-quality services, developed infrastructure, additional convenience features for delegates, and compelling tourist attractions. Scholars emphasize the critical importance of transport accessibility, availability of modern convention centers and mid-to-high-scale hotels, as well as professional human resources in event management (Nurfayziyeva, 2022; Yuniati, 2025).

A separate strand of literature focuses on the institutional architecture of the MICE sector. In several countries and regions—such as Oman, Portugal, and certain Malaysian provinces—Convention Bureaus function as key coordinating entities that mediate between the state, the private sector, and professional conference organizers (ICCA, 2024). Studies by Martín-Rojo and Gaspar-González (2025) demonstrate that in the context of digitalization these structures assume not only marketing and coordination functions but also data analysis related to demand patterns, hybrid formats, and sustainability, guided by GSTC standards and other international criteria (GSTC, 2024; Ilhomova, 2025).

The economic effects of MICE activities are predominantly explored through intersectoral models. Research by Tiecheng and Li (2014), based on empirical data from China, shows that each unit of direct expenditure associated with business events generates up to 2.94 units of total economic output distributed

across trade, energy, printing, hospitality, and telecommunications. Akbar et al. (2024) estimate the multiplier of MICE activity in Kazakhstan at approximately 2.84, underscoring its importance for regional development and cross-border cooperation. Studies by Ubaydullayeva (2025) and Nurfayziyeva (2021) highlight the role of the MICE sector in fostering inclusive tourism, creating jobs, and integrating small businesses into value chains.

Technological trends also constitute a significant area of research. Scholars document a shift from predominantly in-person events to hybrid and virtual formats, increased utilization of VR technologies, live streaming, interactive engagement platforms, and big data analytics (Martín-Rojo & Gaspar-González, 2025; Technavio, 2025). These trends necessitate a rethinking of infrastructure and management approaches in the MICE sector, particularly in developing countries.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

approach that combines qualitative analysis of academic literature with quantitative interpretation of statistical and analytical data. At the first stage, a systematic search was conducted for publications in scholarly journals, conference proceedings, and sectoral reports devoted to MICE tourism development, destination competitiveness, multiplier effects, and institutional structures of the sector. The sample included studies published mainly after 2018, presenting empirical results or rigorous analytical conclusions, as well as reports by international organizations such as ICCA and GSTC, analytical reviews by REAN Intelligence (2024) and Technavio (2025), and national studies on Central Asian countries (Akbar et al., 2024; Ubaydullayeva, 2025; Nurfayziyeva, 2022; Musaeva, 2024).

At the second stage, content analysis was used to identify the key thematic blocks: the structure and definitions of MICE tourism; competitiveness criteria for destinations; institutional models, including Convention Bureaus and the GSTC sustainability criteria (GSTC, 2024); assessments of multiplier effects based on intersectoral models; technological trends; and the specifics of regional cooperation in Central Asia. The quantitative part included tabular representations of global MICE market dynamics, principal indicators of MICE development in Uzbekistan, the distribution of multiplier effects across economic sectors, and technological adoption levels. The obtained data were compared and interpreted with respect to the applicability of international experience to Uzbekistan's conditions.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Forecast estimates presented by REAN Intelligence (2024) and Technavio (2025), summarized in Table 1, indicate consistently high growth rates in the global MICE industry through 2031. A stable trend toward increasing participation of developing countries, particularly in Asia, can be observed, along with a broadening range of event themes, from traditional sector-specific conferences to interdisciplinary forums on the digital economy, sustainable development, and green technologies.

Table-1. Forecast indicators of the global MICE market

Year	Estimated market volume, trillion USD	Approx. growth rate, %	Brief stage characteristic
2024	2.68	-	Baseline year for assessing dynamics
2025	3.26	≈ 21.6	Active recovery of demand
2026	3.96	≈ 21.5	Expansion of business travel and events
2027	4.81	≈ 21.5	Growth of investment activity
2028	5.84	≈ 21.4	Diversification of formats and themes
2029	7.09	≈ 21.4	Consolidation of global mobility trends
2030	8.60	≈ 21.4	Deep integration of digital technologies
2031	10.41	≈ 21.1	Cumulative growth, relative stabilization of rates

These data confirm that MICE tourism is becoming one of the core segments of the global tourism economy. Countries that timely adapt their institutional and infrastructural architecture gain the opportunity to strengthen competitiveness and expand service exports.

Based on national statistical assessments and scholarly analysis (Musaeva, 2024), Table 2 reconstructs the dynamics of MICE development indicators in Uzbekistan in 2022-2023.

Table-2. Dynamics of key indicators of MICE tourism in Uzbekistan

Indicator	2022	2023	Growth rate, %	Absolute change
Number of international conferences	125	150	20.0	+25 events
Average number of participants per conference	1600	2000	25.0	+400 participants
Total MICE revenue, million USD	87	100	14.9	+13 million USD
Number of congress and exhibition centers	-	5	-	Formation of infrastructural base
Total delegate capacity	-	10,000	-	Commissioning of new facilities

The observed increase in events and participants, together with the emergence of a network of congress centers and growth in revenue, indicates the formation of a distinct MICE segment within Uzbekistan's national tourism structure. At the same time, this creates the prerequisites for more active participation of the country in international competition for hosting major business events.

The application of the SFAA model to the analysis of structural criteria for MICE development in Uzbekistan, as shown in Table 3, allows the identification of parameter groups that require strengthening.

Table-3. SFAA model applied to MICE destinations

Parameter group	Subsystem	Brief description	Relative significance
Services	Transport accessibility	International airports, convenient connections, ground logistics	Critical
	Human resources	Staff training in hospitality and event management	High
	Service quality	Service standards, process sustainability	High
Facilities	Hotel infrastructure	Hotels with conference facilities across categories	Critical
	Congress and exhibition venues	Convention centers, multifunctional halls, exhibition complexes	Critical
Amenities	Retail and entertainment	Shopping centers, restaurants, everyday services	Moderate
	Financial services	Currency exchange, payment systems, ATMs	Moderate
	Information support	Tourist offices, informational resources, digital platforms	Moderate
Attractions	Historical and cultural assets	Heritage sites, museums, cultural monuments	Moderate
	Entertainment events	Festivals, concerts, leisure programs	Moderate

As seen, Uzbekistan's strongest potential is associated with the services and facilities blocks: expanding international air connections, developing professional competencies, and modernizing congress and hotel infrastructure.

The analysis of multiplier effects from MICE events in China (Table 4) and Kazakhstan demonstrates the distribution of total economic impact across sectors.

Table-4. Distribution of multiplier effect of MICE events (China)

Sector	Share of total effect, %	Approximate contribution to multiplier	Brief commentary
Wholesale and retail trade	20	0.59 of the total multiplier 2.94	Demand for complementary goods and services
Energy production and supply	17	0.50	Energy intensity of large events
Printing and paper production	15	0.44	Advertising and informational materials

Sector	Share of total effect, %	Approximate contribution to multiplier	Brief commentary
Hospitality and food services	15	0.44	Accommodation and catering for delegates
Telecommunications and ICT	10	0.29	Communication and digital services
Other sectors	23	0.68	Transport, services, and other industries
Total	100	2.94	Integral multiplier

Comparable estimates for Kazakhstan (Akbar et al., 2024) – around 2.84 – indicate strong responsiveness of related industries to the development of MICE tourism. Considering similarities in economic structure, a comparable multiplier potential may be expected for Uzbekistan as MICE activities expand.

The analytics of Technavio (2025) and studies by Martín-Rojo and Gaspar-González (2025), summarized in Table 5, show that digital transformation has become an indispensable component of the modern MICE sector.

Table-5. Prevalence of technological solutions in the MICE sector

Technological solution	Estimated share of organizers or clients using the technology, %	Main users	Impact on sector development
Virtual reality (VR) and immersive formats	≈ 65	Event organizers	Enhanced engagement and presentation quality
Live broadcasting and 360-degree video	≈ 37	Organizers and venues	Expansion of remote audiences
Hybrid (onsite-virtual) formats	≈ 80	Corporate clients	Key format for large international events
Interactive services (polls, online voting)	≈ 57	Organizers and participants	Strengthening feedback and personalization
Virtual venue inspections	≈ 54	MICE industry representatives	Reducing transactional costs when selecting locations
Synchronous interpretation and multilingual platforms	≈ 47	Organizers of international events	Broadening geographical reach

For Uzbekistan, this implies the need for parallel development of physical infrastructure and digital platforms supporting hybrid events with international participation without significantly increasing logistical costs.

Interpretation of results and discussion

Comparison of international experience with the current state of Uzbekistan's MICE sector shows that the country has already achieved notable progress in the number of events, revenue, and the formation of basic congress infrastructure (Musaeva, 2024; Ubaydullayeva, 2025). However, in comparison with leading destinations in the region, the country still lacks large convention centers, specialized hotels, and institutional structures equivalent to Convention Bureaus (ICCA, 2024). Application of the SFAA model demonstrates that priority attention should be given to transportation connectivity, service quality, and the development of accommodation facilities, while cultural attractions already constitute a strong competitive asset. Multiplier estimates by Tiecheng and Li (2014) and Akbar et al. (2024) justify viewing the MICE sector as an instrument for stimulating a broad range of industries, not only tourism and hospitality.

The regional dimension is also important: studies by Akbar et al. (2024) indicate that coordination among Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan in tourism infrastructure development and joint marketing can create synergy and increase the visibility of Central Asia as an integrated business destination. Within such a configuration, Uzbekistan may strengthen its role as a cultural, historical, and scientific hub, capable of hosting major international conferences and forums, while neighboring countries specialize in industry-specific exhibitions and formats that combine MICE activities with ecotourism.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study confirms that MICE tourism is one of the most dynamically developing segments of the global tourism industry and generates significant multiplier effects extending across trade, energy, printing, hospitality, and ICT sectors. For Uzbekistan, this segment represents a window of opportunity associated with

the diversification of the tourism product, growth of export revenues, and deeper integration into international business networks.

Based on the analysis of international experience and empirical assessments, several interrelated directions for developing the MICE sector in Uzbekistan may be proposed. First, it is necessary to strengthen the infrastructural foundation: expand the network of congress and exhibition centers, modernize hotel infrastructure in line with MICE client requirements, and improve transportation connectivity among major cities and tourism clusters. Second, institutional adjustment is essential, including the creation of a national, and subsequently municipal, Convention Bureau capable of serving as a single point of contact for international event organizers, coordinating interactions with state bodies and the private sector, and promoting the country in the global business events market.

Third, active integration of digital and hybrid formats is required, based on established international practices: development of platforms for online registration and streaming, use of VR and AR solutions for presenting venues and exhibitions, and implementation of multilingual interpretation services. Fourth, deeper cross-border cooperation with Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan holds significant potential within a joint strategy for promoting Central Asia as a MICE region, enabling the formation of comprehensive routes and enhancing the competitiveness of each country.

Future research should focus on constructing national intersectoral models to quantitatively assess the contribution of the MICE sector to Uzbekistan's economy, as well as on studying the effects of specific event types on regional development, employment, and inclusive tourism. This will form the basis for more precise adjustment of public policy and support tools for businesses operating in the field of business tourism.

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